

AESTHETIC BALANCE IN THREE DIFFERENT EMOTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Aesthetic balance is an active process of perception to identify i) the regularity and ii) the novelty of a stimulus. This article finds the aesthetic balance of a prototypical web page and establishes the influence of the regularity and the novelty of the product on three affective experiences: beauty, satisfaction and enjoyment. The results show that aesthetic balance equally affects the beauty, while the dimension of regularity leads to satisfaction, and the dimension of novelty leads to enjoyment. The implications of these results are discussed.

KEYWORDS: *Aesthetic Balance, Aesthetic Experience, Design Theory.*

INTRODUCTION

A user's interpretation of a product is a multifaceted experience that can address aesthetic experiences as well as meaningful and affective ones (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). Thus, while an aesthetic experience seeks the delight of the product through different sensory modalities and focuses on the perception of the object, a meaningful experience seeks partnering with various abstract qualities and focuses on the cognition of the product. Finally, affective experience refers to emotions caused by the aesthetic and/or meaningful dimensions of a product on the user. Despite the clear perceptual orientation of the aesthetics, it is known that there are two components that identify i) the regularity and ii) the novelty of the stimulus (Gombrich, 1984). Variations of this double condition determines what is known as aesthetic balance (Coates, 2003), which has been studied under different names in Marketing (Creusen & Snelders, 2002; Creusen & Schoormans, 2005), Architecture (Nasar, 1984, 1999), Design (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Coates, 2003; Locher, Overbeeke & Wensveen, 2010), Semantic Theory (Krippendorff & Butter, 1984; Steffen, 2007, 2009) Visual Arts (Arnheim, 1966; Gombrich, 1984; Hekkert, 2006), Psychology (Russell, 2003; Norman, 2004a; Locher *et al.*, 2007) and Human-Computer Interaction (Tractinsky, Katz & Ikar, 2000; Hassenzahl, 2003; Lindgaard *et al.*, 2006) among others. Given this approach, this article seeks to find the influence of the aesthetic balance of a prototypical web page on three different emotions accord-

ing to Desmet's classification of product emotions (2003): Beauty (aesthetic emotion), Satisfaction (instrumental emotion) and Enjoyment (interest emotion). For this purpose, this article presents a theoretical foundation about aesthetic balance as a two dimensional theoretical construct that captures the regularity -Classical Aesthetics- and novelty -Expressive Aesthetic- of a product (Gombrich, 1984, Lavie & Tractinsky, 2004). To test the Balance Aesthetic, first a group of experts analyzed the learning platform of the University of Nariño looking at prototypical forms of regularity and novelty following Reber, Shwarz & Winkielman (2004). Second, the validity and reliability of the scales used to measure the classical and expressive dimensions were determined. Subsequently, each of these dimensions was correlated with beauty to compare individual variance that was explained using a nested model procedure (Edwards, 2001; Burton-Jones & Straub, 2006). Following Coates (2003) and Tractinsky *et al.* (2006), equilibrium between these two dimensions and beauty is expected. Finally, the impact of excluding each of the dimensions in the explained variance of beauty, satisfaction and enjoyment has been determined. With this procedure, we expected to find the different impacts of aesthetic balance on the chosen emotions. Thus, a greater impact on the exclusion of classical aesthetics on satisfaction (Lindgaard & Dudek, 2003), as well as a greater impact on the exclusion of expressive aesthetics on the enjoyment (Sanchez-Franco & Roldan, 2005) is expected.

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

As part of the aesthetic experience, beauty is an active process of perception between the formal characteristics of the stimulus and the sensory modalities of the person that seeks to find the balance between i) regularity and ii) novelty underlying an object (Arnheim, 1966, Gombrich, 1984; Coates, 2003). The interaction of these attributes provides different affective responses to the product that can range from visceral emotions to deeper affective evaluations (Desmet, 2003; Hekkert, 2006; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007; Norman 2004a, 2004b). This double condition is a part of the discussion between Objective Aesthetic and Subjective Aesthetics. That is, whether beauty is a property of the object or a person's judgment. The importance of this issue lies in the fact that the appeal could be addressed as a perceptual stimulus (e.g. Gestalt psychology), or as a subjective judgment (e.g. product Semiotics). If it is done using the first approach, the aesthetic experience is reduced to an innate mechanism that recognizes simple patterns of survival and formal identification (e.g. Karvonen, 2000, Norman, 1988). In contrast, if undertaken using the second approach, it is assumed that an aesthetic experience is first of all meaningful, where the cognitive exercise and symbolic judgments of the observer come first (e.g. Pickford, 1972; Hassenzahl, 2003; Hassenzahl, 2004b). As pointed out by Lavie & Tractinsky (2004), current theories have assumed an intermediate position in which beauty is approached from the characteristics of the stimulus and the individual's expectations. Meanwhile, Gombrich (1984) believes that the importance of this discussion focuses on an intermediate point where the underlying regularity of the stimulus is investigated, as well as the discovery of deviations that raise our affect for novelty.

It is important to note that in this study, the author assumes that judgments of aesthetic experiences are different from the judgments of meaningful experiences (Crilly, Moultrie & Clarkson, 2004; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007), because the former are related to the formal components of a product, whereas the latter are related to its functional interpretations and symbolic associations (Hassenzahl, 2008). From this perspective, it is necessary to distinguish between the three levels of mental processing to measure the aesthetic: Visceral, Cognitive and Reflective (Norman, 2004a). When approached as a set of attributes that evaluate the formal characteristics of the product, it is considered a measure of visceral aesthetic (e.g. Lavie & Tractinsky, 2004); however, if approached as a set of attributes that evaluate the functional and symbolic associations (e.g. Hassenzahl, 2003) it is considered a measure with cognitive or reflective emphasis (Tractinsky, 2004). Following Norman (2004b), the approach taken in this paper holds that the aesthetic balance is associated with the visceral level of processing. However, the beauty, satisfaction and enjoyment as general and abstract emotional responses are associated with the level of reflective processing (Hassenzahl, 2004b; Desmet & Hekkert, 2007) as shown in Figure 1.

Aesthetic Balance

The measurement of beauty from aesthetic balance has been used by various authors such as Nasar (1984; 1999) with the attributes of order and diversity in the city, Steffen (2007; 2009) with the concepts of order and complexity in product language of clothing, Coates (2003) with the factors of information and concinnity, and Lavie & Tractinsky (2004) with the dimensions of classical and expressive aesthetics, among others. In all the previous examples, it is implicitly assumed that beauty is a higher order theoretical construction consisting of this double condition. It is evident that any variation in this duality will involve changes in perception and judgment of the product. This is illustrated by Arnheim (1966) when he claims that the complexity without order produces confusion and order without complexity produces boredom. Similarly, Gombrich (1984) states that aesthetic pleasure lays somewhere between boredom and confusion and Reber et al. (2004) agree when talking about perceptual fluency. Coates (2003) is more specific and assumes that the aesthetic ingredients of a product resemble a balance between factors of Information and Concinnity. The information factor is based on Shannon & Weaver (1949)'s model of information codification between the object and the person as a communication system. Thus, the difference of contrast and novelty between the mental model and the *expected object* is measured in the product. The increase of contrast and novelty, expands the information that is reflected as increased cognitive arousal. On the other hand, the concinnity factor measures the normality of the product attributes and the similarity between the mental model and the *hoped object*. The increase of concinnity increases compatibility, which is reflected in less information and cognitive interest. Only if there is a balance between novelty and concinnity is there an adequate amount of information and therefore a positive visual attractiveness is obtained (i.e. positive valence). In contrast, if there is only cognitive arousal, the appeal will be confusing and if concinnity also exists, the appeal will be neutral or boring. It can be said then that the aesthetic balance consists in the variations between dimensions that measure the perception of regularity and the novelty of the product. Following Lavie and Tractinsky (2004), it is believed that this approach to measuring this double condition improves users' analysis and understanding to judge the beauty and other emotions of a stimulus. Thus, it is suggested that satisfaction is an affective reaction given by the stimulus of perceived regularity while enjoyment is an affective reaction given by the stimulus of perceived novelty. In the case of beauty, the affective reaction is a value judgment resulting from the balance between regularity and novelty.

METHOD

Considering the theoretical background, it can be said that the structure of aesthetic balance is modeled as an aggregate construct with two composite dimensions that jointly capture the regularity and novelty of the product. The scale to measure each of these dimensions is based on Lavie & Tractinsky

(2004)'s Classical and Expressive Aesthetics. This scale was chosen for several reasons: (1) it is a scale designed to measure the user's experience beyond the experts' experience. This is important because the validation was carried out with a group of engineering students who did not have a comprehensive knowledge of the aesthetic issue. (2) It is a scale comprised of two dimensions: one designed to measure the regularity of the product and the other, designed to measure the novelty of the product. This scale also shows good reliability of data obtained through a process of four studies. (3) It is a scale that has been replicated in other studies, especially in the measurement of different websites (see Sutcliffe & De Angeli, 2005; De Angeli, Sutcliffe & Hartmann, 2006; Hartmann, Sutcliffe, & De Angeli, 2008).

Thus, from the original scale, the following terms of the classical dimension were extracted: Symmetric, Clear, and Pleasant. The following terms of the expressive dimension were also extracted: Original, Sophisticated, and Fascinating. Finally, the terms Ordered and Complexity were added (Arnheim, 1966; Steffen, 2007, 2009) for each of the dimensions proposed.

Design

Prior to the study, a group of experts in web design - consisting of five doctoral students in Multimedia Engineering from the Polytechnic University of Catalonia - found in the virtual campus of University of Nariño (<http://uvirtual.udenar.edu.co/>) easily identifiable prototypical forms of symmetry, figure-ground contrast, visual clarity and information (Reber et al., 2004). Figure 2 shows the screenshot of the platform

CONSTRUCT	ITEMS
Classic Aesthetic	CA1. The virtual campus is ordered
	CA2. The virtual campus is symmetric
	CA3. The virtual campus is clear
	CA4. The virtual campus is pleasant
Expressive Aesthetic	EA5. The virtual campus is complexity
	EA6. The virtual campus is original
	EA7. The virtual campus is sophisticated
	EA8. The virtual campus is fascinating
Beauty	B9. The virtual campus is beauty
Satisfaction	S10. The interaction with the virtual campus has been satisfactory
	S11. The interaction with the virtual campus has been a positive experience
Enjoyment	E12. I enjoyed using the virtual campus
	E13. The interaction with the virtual campus has been a pleasant experience
	E14. Experience with the virtual campus has been enjoyable

Table 1: Measurement Scales

where it is possible to see the web page fulfilling the criterion of prototypical stimulus. To Reber et al. (2004) all prototypical stimuli allow better perceptual fluency and greater aesthetic experience.

The study involved one hundred and thirty-three engineering students from the University of Nariño (44 female and 89 male whose age average was 19), in an online survey based on their impressions of the virtual campus of the university. Students assessed the new website design using a 5-point scale ranging from (1) "Strongly disagree" to (5) "Strongly agree". In addition to assessing product regularity and novelty, students were asked to rate the Beauty of the website (aesthetic emotion), Satisfaction (instrumental emotion) and Enjoyment (interest emotion) obtained when using this educational platform following Desmet's (2003) classification of product emotions. Thus, beauty is seen as a more general and abstract emotional response (Hassenzahl, 2004b) resulting from the aesthetic balance of the product. The items regarding Satisfaction were taken from Hong, Thong & Tam (2006), and the ones concerning Enjoyment were taken from Sanchez-Franco & Roldan (2005). The final questionnaire contained 14 items, as shown in Table 1.

RESULTS

Table 2 shows the results obtained with the factorial loadings and the reliability of the scale. The Composite Reliability (CR) and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) were obtained using the PLS-Graph software, and the factor loadings and Cronbach's alpha using SPSS software. The term Pleasant (CA4) was excluded because it was loaded on Expressive Aesthetics (0.502) and the term Complexity was excluded (EA5) to improve the Cronbach's alpha coefficient (0.550 if item is not deleted) on the Expressive Aesthetics. Following Nunnally (1978), a value of 0.7 will be a reliable "modest" in early stages of research and a stricter value 0.8 will be more appropriate for basic research. Thus, the two dimensions showed adequate reliability to overcome the suggested minimum value.

In terms of validation, Table 3 shows the discriminant validity of the dimensions by means of the square root of AVE that should be above 0.50 in the diagonal of the table, thus, establishing that over 50% of the variance of construct is due to its indicators (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). Besides beauty, the results obtained with satisfaction and enjoyment were included for later discussion.

Testing Nested Models

Following Edwards (2001) and Burton-Jones & Straub (2006), each of the aesthetic dimensions was first tested separately by examining the values of the variance explained (R^2) on beauty with the software PLS-Graph and using bootstrapping technique with 500 re-sampling and centroid. Next, the two dimensions were tested together but as separate components, and finally the two composite dimensions were tested as an aggregate construct called Aesthetic Balance. As expected, it

was found that there is a higher amount of R² when aesthetic balance is used as an aggregate theoretical construct, namely as a theoretical definition resulting from the combination of its dimensions. Table 4 shows the results obtained.

The higher-order model was constructed using factor scores for each sub-construct.

As models of Table 4 are nested, it is possible to compare the degree to which each of the dimensions of aesthetic balance explains the beauty of the website as well as the satisfaction and enjoyment. To measure the relative impact of the dimensions on these three constructs, the change in the value of R² when any one of the dimensions is removed was compared. The effect size (*f*²) was calculated by the formula $(R^2_{full} - R^2_{excluded}) \div (1 - R^2_{full})$ (Mathieson, et al, 2001). For his part,

Cohen (1988) suggests an *f*² of 0.02 as small, 0.15 as medium and 0.35 as large (see Chin, 1998). Multiplying *f*² by (*n* - *k* - 1) where *n* is the sample size and *k* is the number of independent variables, it is possible to obtain a pseudo F test to the statistical significance of *f*² (Mathieson et. al 2001). Table 5 shows the results obtained. As expected, the greater impact to exclude the regularity—classical aesthetic—was on the satisfaction, whereas the greater impact to exclude novelty—expressive aesthetic—was on the enjoyment.

Figure 3 shows the *f*² for the three measured emotions. As expected, the change in aesthetic balance is more balanced in terms of beauty than in the other emotions. Below, the implications of the results are discussed.

DISCUSSION

The aesthetic balance is primarily associated with the visceral level of processing a stimulus as shown by other studies (Berlyne, 1971; Tractinsky, et al 2006; Lindgaard et al, 2006). However, the affective reaction based on the fluency variations of aesthetic balance produce (Reber et al., 2006), influences the emotional responses associated with the level of reflective processing. The findings in this study show that the aesthetic balance can be a good predictor of three different emotions: Beauty (aesthetic emotion) Satisfaction (instrumental emotion) and Enjoyment (interest emotion). Each relationship is discussed next.

ITEM	CLASSIC AESTHETIC	EXPRESSIVE AESTHETIC	COMPOSITE RELIABILITY
CA1	0.647***	0.292	0.845
CA2	0.631***	0.208	
CA3	0.750***	0.150	
EA6	0.353	0.576***	0.784
EA7	0.179	0.760***	
EA8	0.199	0.570***	

*** All item-to-construct loadings are significant (*p* < 0.001).

Table 2: Measurement Scales for aesthetic dimensions

	CLASSIC AESTHETIC	EXPRESSIVE AESTHETIC	SATISFACTION	ENJOYMENT	BEAUTY
Classic Aesthetic	0.803*				
Expressive Aesthetic	0.501	0.741*			
Satisfaction	0.601	0.470	0.901*		
Enjoyment	0.530	0.474	0.574	0.878*	
Beauty	0.437	0.459	0.524	0.486	1.000

*The values in bold on the diagonal are the square root of each construct's AVE. Off-diagonal elements are correlations between constructs.

Table 3: Discriminant validity for aesthetic dimensions

MODEL	PATH COEFFICIENTS /WEIGHT	T-STATISTICS	R ²
[AB_1]	BCA= 0.452	TCA= 4.801***	R ² =0.204
	BEA= 0.471	TEA= 7.322***	R ² =0.222
[AB_2]	BCA= 0.291	TCA= 2.319*	R ² =0.286
	BEA= 0.328	TEA= 2.954**	
[AB_3]	WCA= 0.257	TAB= 10.028***	R ² =0.314
	BAB= 0.560		
	WEA= 0.242		

CA= Classical Aesthetic; EA= Expressive Aesthetic; AB= Aesthetic Balance; B= the path coefficient between an antecedent and beauty.; W= The weight of the subconstruct on the higher order usage construct in PLS. t-value significant at **p*<0.5, ***p*<0.01, ****p*<0.001.

Table 4: Structural Models Tested

EMOTIONS	R ² FULL	CLASSIC AESTHETIC			EXPRESSIVE AESTHETIC		
		R ² EXCLUDED	f ²	EFFECT SIZE	R ² EXCLUDED	f ²	EFFECT SIZE
Beauty	0.31	0.22	0.13*	small	0.20	0.16*	medium
Satisfaction	0.44	0.22	0.39*	large	0.36	0.13*	small
Enjoyment	0.39	0.24	0.24*	large	0.28	0.18*	medium

*significant at pseudo F test (see Mathieson, et al, 2001).

Table 5: Exclusion Impact of Dimensions of Aesthetic Balance

Aesthetic Balance and Beauty

Following the relations of Figure 1, beauty is understood as a high-level evaluative construct measured by the balance between the perception of regularity—classical aesthetics—and perception of novelty—aesthetic-expressive—both potential determinants of low level (Hassenzahl, 2004a) known as aesthetic balance (Coates, 2003). This double condition allows us to use the aesthetic balance as an aggregate construct, which is only a composite of its dimensions that when combined produce a better explained variance of the studied theoretical issue (Law, Wong & Mobley, 1998). Among the benefits of taking the aesthetic balance as an aggregate construct are (1) it can provide holistic representations of a complex phenomenon as aesthetic experience, (2) many of the important results in research about aesthetic are factorially complex and can only be explained through predictors composite, and (3) it is possible to evaluate specific dimensions of aesthetic balance by the process of nested models (for more information about constructs see Law et al, 1998; Edwards & Bagozzi, 2000; Edwards, 2001; Petter, Straub & Rai, 2007). Thus, Table 4 allows us to conclude that the balance aesthetic as an aggregate construct better explains beauty with its combined dimensions ($R^2 = 0.314$) than with its dimensions separately ($R^2 = 0.286$). Similarly, it can be seen that in the first two models in Table 4, the influence of the expressive dimension on the variance of beauty is superior to the classical dimension - in the first model $BCA = 0.45$ vs. $BEA = 0.47$, and the second model $BCA = 0.29$ vs. $BEA = 0.32$. Given that the evaluated website is clearly task-oriented, one would expect to see greater influence of the classical dimension on the expressive dimension (see Davis, Bagozzi & Warshaw, 1992; Hassenzahl, 2003; Sanchez-Franco & Roldan, 2005; Hassenzahl & Monk, 2010). However, this only happens in the third model when the influence of the dimensions as part of an aggregate construct is studied ($WCA = 0.25$ vs. $WEA = 0.24$). This adjustment, besides the explained variance, suggests better outcomes for aesthetic balance as an aggregate construct to measure beauty.

On the other hand, the similarity of the data found between the classical dimension ($r = 0.43$, $f^2 = 0.13$) and the expressive dimension ($r = 0.45$, $f^2 = 0.16$), confirms the approach of Coates (2003) on the equilibrium of aesthetic balance and beauty as an affective experience. It is possible to say then that beauty is an evaluative judgment that measures the balance between the novelty and regularity of a product. Additionally, this equilibrium changes over time and with the target user's profile. For

example, the degree of novelty always decreases over time until the appearance of the product becomes familiar to the user. The same applies to user expectations, because the novelty depends on the comparative difference between the expected experience and the gained experience (Coates, 2003). When analyzing the results of the aesthetic balance of a product this should always be considered. In the case of the evaluated website in this study, the highest correlation and impact of the expressive dimension is explained by the recent design of the web interface and the user's profile with little experience of working in Learning Management Systems (LMS). Unlike the expressive dimension, the classical dimension is objective and therefore more predictable. Concepts such as symmetry, order and contrast never change over time and perhaps for this reason they tend to be judged with higher interpersonal homogeneity (Gombrich, 1984; Coates, 2003; Hassenzahl, 2008). Thus, the classical dimension measures the compatibility between the hoped regularity and the obtained regularity. For example, the website under study is task-oriented and therefore we expect a degree of regularity that does not distract or confuse users with irrelevant or noisy information.

Aesthetic Balance, Satisfaction and Enjoyment

The results in Table 3 and Table 5 show the variations of aesthetic balance and their respective influence on satisfaction and enjoyment, which are consistent with the results of other investigations. In the case of the classical dimension, it was found that their influence on the satisfaction variable has the highest correlation ($r = 0.60$) and impact ($f^2 = 0.39$). According to Lindgaard & Dudek (2003), satisfaction is a complex construct with several affective components linked to the expected use. For this reason, it is an emotion that is geared towards goal achievement (Desmet, 2003) that has been used to confirm the user's expectations (Oliver, 1993). Thus, we expected to find a higher influence of the classical dimension on satisfaction than on other affective experiences. In the case of the expressive dimension, findings showed that their influence on enjoyment has the highest correlation ($r = 0.47$) and impact ($f^2 = 0.18$). Enjoyment has been used as a construct of the user's intrinsic motivation (Davis et al, 1992), and this means that it seeks to measure the pleasure of a person to engage in any activity while browsing or trying to understand something new (Vallerand & Rattele, 2002). These types of activities that do not require apparent reinforcement (Sanchez-Franco & Roldan, 2005) but raise interest in the novelty of product are geared towards measuring the hedonic characteristics of

	SATISFACTION	BEAUTY	ENJOYMENT
Definition	Positive reflective response to the existence of more regularity in the aesthetic balance	Positive reflective response to the existence of equality between regularity and innovation in the aesthetic balance	Positive reflective response to the existence of more novelty in the aesthetic balance
Feature	Oriented to device and extrinsic motivations	Oriented aesthetic experience (user + artifact)	Oriented to user and intrinsic motivations
Example	Learning Management System (moodle)	Social Network	
(Facebook)	Microbloggings		
(Templates Tumblr)			
Graph	[Graph_Satisfaction]	[Graph_Beauty]	[Graph_Enjoyment]
CA= Classical Aesthetic; EA= Expressive Aesthetic; AB= Aesthetic Balance.			

Table 6: Aesthetic Balance and emotional dimensions

a system (Desmet, 2003; Heijden, 2004). Thus, the influence of the expressive dimension on enjoyment is consistent with the results found.

Aesthetic Balance and Design

Finally, it is important to note that this study focuses on the design as a communication process whereby the product is the linkage between the designer's intentions and the user's interpretations (Crilly, Matravers & Clarkson, 2008; Crilly, Maier & Clarkson, 2008). The results obtained here are centered on the user's interpretations and they are analyzed as an experience of access to information in relation to products based on their emotional dimensions, as proposed in Table 6.

This narrative experience of the product (Dunne & Raby, 2001; Djajadiningrat et al, 2004) can be used to measure the balance of the aesthetic appearance of the product. However, it could also serve as input for other studies to determine the degree of aesthetic innovation from the expressive dimension (Steffen, 2007) or the aesthetics of the interaction from the classical dimension and its relation to usability (Overbeeke & Wensveen, 2003).

It is important to highlight that this approach to double aesthetic conditions, does not affect the possibilities of considering beauty from only one dimension. We believe that taking a unique conceptualization about this topic is impossible; however, we also believe that there are appropriate measures and dimensions that can be used separately or together to support a study of the aesthetic experience.

LIMITATIONS

One of the major limitations in these types of studies is to measure beauty based on cultural differences (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). We believe that this aspect is compensated with the validity, reliability and different replications of the selected scale in other studies. Although Cronbach's alpha in

the expressive dimension was poor (0.572), the result of the composite reliability (0.784) is considered as a superior measure because the loads are fixed in the unit (Barclay, Higgins & Thompson, 1995). It is emphasized that the term *pleasant* is loaded to the expressive dimension and not to the classical dimension as expected. For Coates (2003) and Russell & Carroll (1999), this term is close to the valence dimension where the classical aesthetic is measured. However, to Hassenzahl (2004a) this term has an evaluative component that could explain the load to the expressive dimension. Another possible explanation is that the Spanish adaptation to the term has changed its semantic load. However, the translation was made taking into account the adaptation of Gurbindo & Ortega (1989) on Russell's scale. The same applies to the term *complexity* that people associate with the meaning of "confusing" instead of the interrelated parts of a system (Norman, 2010). For this reason, in the evaluation of the website, these terms were not taken into account. Even so, discriminatory validity and test nested models show that the scale is valid to measure the beauty of the product.

CONCLUSIONS

The results obtained indicate that the aesthetic balance can be used as a higher order theoretical aggregate construct with two dimensions that measure the regularity—classical aesthetics—and novelty—expressive aesthetic—of the product. Similarly, the study shows that the aesthetic balance can be a good predictor of beauty and other affective experiences such as satisfaction and enjoyment. Regularity influences the affective experiences oriented to the evaluation of tasks such as satisfaction, while novelty influences the affective experiences oriented to the user's intrinsic motivation such as enjoyment. Likewise, regularity and novelty influence beauty when it is treated as an evaluative judgment. Thus, beauty seeks the balance between the novelty and the regularity that a person perceives in a product. Finally, the double fold condition of aesthetic balance allows the use of its dimensions as inputs

in various research approaches about aesthetics such as Aesthetic Innovation or Aesthetics of Interaction.

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